

ASSESSMENT OF THE THREE PILLARS OF THE COMPREHENSIVE DISASTER RISK REDUCTION MANAGEMENT IN BASIC EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Disasters are inevitable, but their scope and magnitude are often magnified due to unsustainable development that has not considered the possible hazard impacts in a particular location. Compliance with DRRM should be identified as one of the primary concerns of any school to prepare necessary precautionary measures in the occurrence of natural and even human-caused calamities. This study entitled “Assessment of the Three Pillars of the Comprehensive Disaster Risk Reduction Management in Basic Education” sought to establish significant relationships between the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of the teacher respondents, as well as with the school profile of the 48 participating schools using Chi-Square Test. Best Practices for the implementation of the DRRM activities were also analyzed. The test of hypotheses conducted in this study has recognized the significant relationship between variables that are notably important to the teachers, schools, pillars of the DRRM, and most importantly, to the learners. The study's results displayed a significant relationship between the teachers' attitudes, together with the enrollment profile, and the extent of the level of implementation of the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education. Having a high score on the CFSS also significantly correlates with the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education.

Keywords: *Disaster risk reduction management, hazard, resilience, Philippines, community involvement*

INTRODUCTION

The world has experienced increased exposure to risks and hazards of climate-related and human-made disasters that threaten lives and sustainable development efforts (Lopez et al., 2018). In the study of Manalo (2019), the situation needs attention. Therefore, disaster capacity and mitigation efforts can be formulated to reduce population exposure and vulnerability in international and local settings. Disasters are inevitable, but their scope and magnitude are often magnified due to unsustainable development that has not considered the possible hazard impacts in a particular location. The effects of such can be minimized if the population has a better understanding of locally experienced hazards and implements corresponding preventive or mitigating measures.

Disasters, with their potential to cause deaths and severe societal disruptions, necessitate the global community to take decisive actions to address and reduce their impacts. In recognition of this, the Philippine government, through the Disaster Risk Reduction Management Act of 2010, has mandated the integration of disaster risk reduction into the school curriculum. This initiative aims to enhance the awareness and practice of personnel and students in calamity preparedness (Ventura & Madrigal, 2020).

The Philippines, with its high exposure to natural hazards and limited resources for managing them, faces a critical need for accurate forecasts and evidence-based allocation of available funding for disaster preparedness and relief. In this context, Disaster Risk Managers play a pivotal role. A survey conducted in 2016–2017 revealed significant disparities in how Managers perceive risk and their levels of preparedness across the country, influenced by varying storm impacts since 2009. To facilitate effective policymaking, the collection of more comprehensive and up-to-date data is imperative (Brucal et al., 2020).

In the Philippines, an earthquake happened which disrupted Education throughout the Bohol Region. The damage to education infrastructure was extensive, based on the Bohol Earthquake Action Plan (2013). Multiple schools were rendered unusable because of damage, and some are due to prolonged use as shelters.

As cited by Benson (2016), in the event of a disaster causes significant financing gaps in many developing countries. It means the economy may fall back instead on reallocating planned capital and recurrent spending to meet more immediate post-disaster spending requirements and often redirect capital budgets over the years. Unsafe schools will continue to betray the trust and hope that is placed in them unless schools are conscious and proactive. Learners will get injured and drop out of schools in vast numbers unless the responsibility is jointly taken to make them safe. School's Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) program implementation has a more significant favorable influence on the lives of the learners (Bello, 2020). Natural disasters have increased dramatically in frequency and intensity (Kron, 2015).

In this research, the author aims to assess the level of implementation of the three pillars of disaster risk reduction management in basic education in the District of Santa Maria as per DO 37, s. 2015. Compliance with DRRM should be identified as one of the primary concerns of any school to prepare necessary preventive measures in the occurrence of natural and even human-caused calamities.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the school, in terms of location, enrollment, position of school head, position of coordinator, school-based management level and child friendly school survey level?
 2. What is the level of knowledge, skills, and attitudes of teachers on the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM in basic education?
 3. What is the extent of implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education, in terms of?
 - 3.1 Safe Learning Facilities?
 - 3.2 School Disaster Management?
 - 3.3 Risk Reduction and Resilience Education?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of knowledge, skills, and attitudes of teachers on the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM in basic education and the extent of implementation of the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the school and level of knowledge, skills, and attitudes of teachers on the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM in basic education?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the school and the extent of implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education?
 7. What are the common and best practices of elementary and secondary schools with regard with the implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in basic Education?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research used descriptive evaluative design. A descriptive evaluative research design is a methodological approach that aims to gather information about prevailing conditions or situations for the purpose of description and interpretation (Fikri et al., 2021).

This method was used to describe and analyze the data on the implementations of DRRM in Basic Education for this study.

Sampling Technique

According to Kang's study (2021), G*Power is a tool for computing statistical power analyses for many different t-tests, F-tests, Chi-squared tests, z-tests and some exact tests. This was used to determine the samples which will be used for the quantitative part of the study.

Purposive sampling was used. A purposive sample is the one whose characteristics are defined for a purpose that is relevant to the study (Andrade, 2021). The main purpose is to gather information by surveying the DRRM coordinators and their school heads of each school in the District of Santa Maria. There were 48 respondents in total.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a questionnaire approved and content validated by the defense panel. Validation of the questionnaire was made to secure the reliability and dependability of the questions as per suggestions and corrections made by the members of the panel. The questionnaire that was used in gathering data was divided into two parts. The first part includes the profile of the school as per the data available in the school reports. It specifically includes name of the school, location, enrollment, position of the school head, position of the school DRRM coordinator, SBM level, and CFSS points.

Part two was a multiple-choice type of examination that aided the author in determining the teacher respondents' level of knowledge, skill, and attitude regarding the three pillars of comprehensive disaster risk reduction management.

Part three assessed the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in primary Education using a five-point Likert's Scale. Pillar I (Safe Learning Facilities) includes critical indicators on two aspects: education facilities that are conducive to the physical well-being of learners and a secure learning environment that promotes the protection and mental and emotional well-being of learners. Pillar II (School Disaster Management) includes leadership and coordination, information management, school and community stakeholders' engagement and participation, student-led activities, and education continuity plans. The last was Pillar III (Risk Reduction and Resilience Education), which included DRRM integration in the K to 12 Curriculum, co-curricular activities, learning materials and strategies, and a national greening program.

An open-ended question was also included for the SDRRM coordinators and the school head. This noted the best practices of his respective schools regarding implementing the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM in basic Education that can be shared with other schools.

This study began with the pilot implementation. A pilot implementation of a study is a small-scale preliminary study conducted before any large-scale quantitative research to evaluate the potential for a future, full-scale project. It is considered a fundamental stage of the research process, for it can help identify design issues and evaluate a study's feasibility, practicality, resources, time, and cost before the main research is conducted.

The pilot implementation enables researchers to predict an appropriate sample size, budget accordingly, and improve the study design before performing a full-scale project. The study was piloted to all elementary SDRRM Coordinators and Key teachers of the Mabitac Sub-Office respondents.

Data Collection and Analysis

The author has the pertinent documents approved by proper authority to conduct this study. Communication lines and coordination with responsible persons was also be ensured for proper distribution and retrieval of the raw data needed.

A survey was conducted, and the researcher visits all the schools in order to gather all the necessary data from the school DRRM coordinators and school heads, for them to answer the survey. It was also noted to remind the respondents of the confidentiality of their answers. The answers in the open- ended questions were noted and highlighted through citation of best practices.

As for the analysis of data, the parameters are presented with the corresponding statistical tools. They were used for a more valid and more reliable interpretation and analysis of data.

The profile of the school, and the assessment of the level of knowledge, skill, and attitude of teachers on the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM used frequency and percentage. A percentage frequency distribution is a display of data that specifies the percentage of observations that exist for each data point or grouping of data points. It is a particularly useful method of expressing the relative frequency of survey responses and other data (Khan et al., 2018).

The assessment of the extent of implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education used weighted means. Significant relationship between the level of knowledge, skill, and attitude of teachers on the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM and extent of implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in basic education used the test of relationship called the chi-squared test.

For the significant relationship between the profile of the school and the extent of implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in basic education, this study used the chi- squared test. Chi square testing can also be used to determine if two categorical variables are associated with each other. The variables being analyzed do not have to have the same number of levels (Chen, 2021).

RESULTS

Table 1. Profile of the Schools

Location	Frequency	Percentage
Upland	18	37.50
Lowland	26	54.17
Town Proper	4	8.33
Total	48	100.00

Enrollment	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 250	34	70.83
251-500	10	20.83
501-750	0	0.00
751 and Above	4	8.33
Total	48	100.00

Position of the School Head	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher Leader	0	0.00
Teacher In Charge	14	29.17
Head Teacher	14	29.17
Principal	20	41.67
Total	48	100.00

Position of the School DRRM Coordinator	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher I	20	41.67
Teacher II	13	27.08
Teacher III	14	29.17
Head Teacher/ Master Teacher	1	2.08
Total	48	100.00

School Based Management Level	Frequency	Percentage
Level 1 (Developing)	0	0.00
Level 2 (Maturing)	38	79.17

Level 3 (Advanced)	10	20.83
Total	48	100.00
Child Friendly School Survey Level	Frequency	Percentage
30-below	8	16.67
31 to 35	10	20.83
36 to 40	30	62.50
Total	48	100.00

Table 2. Level of Knowledge of Teachers on the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

Competency	No. of Items	Highest Score	Lowest Score	Mean	SD	MPS
Knowledge	10	10	4	7.75	1.56	77.50
Item				Number of Correct Responses	Item Difficulty Index	
DRRM means.				47	0.98	
National and provincial hazard maps have been prepared to increase knowledge of risks and at the same time influence development of policies and programs.				48	1.00	
This pillar refers to the establishment of organizational support structures such as the DRRM Service and DRRM Coordinators in all regional and division offices of DepEd.				37	0.77	
This refers to the integration of DRRM in the formal and non-formal school curricula and in extracurricular activities.				41	0.85	
How many times do we conduct the Nationwide Simultaneous Earthquake Drill?				48	1.00	
Disaster risk management involves activities related to the following except for one:				28	0.58	
Which of the following is the correct approach of the DRR's Innovation curve?				38	0.79	

Which is identified as the appropriate communication of robust risk information at the right time can raise awareness and trigger action.	28	0.58
Which is identified as the understanding of the geographic area affected, along with the intensity and frequency of hazard events, planning evacuation routes, creating shelters, and running preparedness drills.	27	0.56
Which is identified as the risk information for reconstruction needs to be available before an event occurs, since after the event there is rarely time to collect the data needed to inform resilient design and land-use plans.	30	0.63

Table 3. Level of Skills of Teachers on the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

Competency	No. of Items	Highest Score	Lowest Score	Mean	SD	MPS
Skills	10	10	4	8,25	1.56	82.50
Item				Number of Correct Responses	Item Difficulty Index	
What do you call the initial care for an ill or injured person?				48	1.00	
In giving first aid treatment, the first step is to _____.				34	0.71	
Which of the following is not a type of sports injury?				36	0.75	
In the prevention of communicable disease and illness, _____ is essential.				40	0.83	
During an emergency procedure, recognizing respiratory or cardiac arrest and the proper application of CPR is called as _____.				39	0.81	
Basic Life Support is performed to support the patient's _____ through the use of CPR until advanced life support arrives.				45	0.94	
In doing the CPR in adult, how many breaths should be given every 30 compression?				33	0.69	
It is the first aid given when a person is choking.				43	0.90	

If an emergency patient has fractured arm or leg, this supportive device is used to keep in place any suspected fracture.	44	0.92
Which one is not a goal of DRR?	34	0.71

Table 4. Level of Attitudes of Teachers on the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

Competency	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Attitude			
In the occurrence of earthquakes, floods, or other disasters, our school is adequately prepared.	4.60	Very High	6.5
Hazard mapping is done and properly addressed.	4.60	Very High	6.5
Training of teachers and other stakeholders is conducted.	4.48	Very High	9
Drills for disaster preparedness are conducted every quarter.	4.85	Very High	1
In case of disaster occurrence, evacuation maps are visible and are strategically placed for the learners to be seen.	4.67	Very High	5
In case of disaster occurrence, emergency contact numbers are visible and are strategically placed for easy access.	4.69	Very High	3.5
A disaster kit is always ready and available.	4.73	Very High	2
Monitoring of news and forecasts for preparedness for disasters and calamities.	4.69	Very High	3.5
It is easy to contact response teams because the school has an available communication device.	4.50	Very High	8
Transport for emergency cases is simple because there is an available transport service.	4.06	High	10
Average Weighted Mean	4.59	Very High	

Table 5. Extent of Implementation of the Three Pillars of the Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education in terms of Safe Learning Facilities

Pillar I Safe Learning Facilities	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
is accessible to all, regardless of physical ability.	4.542	Very High	6.5
the learning environment is marked by visible boundaries and clear signs, as appropriate.	4.500	Very High	8.5
the grounds have adequate space for classes and administration, recreation, and sanitation facilities.	4.375	High	14.5
the class space and seating arrangements are according to the prescribed ratio of space per learner and teacher, at all grade levels, to facilitate participatory methodologies and learner-centered approaches.	4.563	Very High	5
the community participates in the construction and maintenance of the school.	4.375	High	14.5
basic health and hygiene are promoted in the learning environment.	4.708	Very High	1
adequate sanitation facilities are provided, considering age, gender, and special education needs and considerations.	4.667	Very High	2
adequate quantities of water for safe drinking and personal hygiene are available at the learning site.	4.500	Very High	8.5
is near the populations they serve.	4.458	High	12
there are access routes leading to the school that are safe and secure for all.	4.479	High	10.5
the learning environment is free from dangers that may cause harm to learners.	4.396	High	13
training programs for teachers, learners, and the community are in place to promote safety, security, and protection.	4.542	Very High	6.5
teachers and other education personnel are provided with the skills to give psychosocial support for the learners' emotional well-being.	4.479	High	10.5

the community is involved in decisions concerning the location of the learning environment, and in establishing systems and policies to ensure that learners are safe and secure.	4.604	Very High	4
the nutrition and short-term hunger need of learners are addressed to allow for effective learning to take place at the learning site.	4.646	Very High	3
Average Weighted Mean	4.522	Very High	

Table 6. Extent of Implementation of the Three Pillars of the Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education in terms of School Disaster Management

Pillar II School Disaster Management	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
the DRRM was headed by the school head.	4.771	Very High	1.5
teachers and other school personnel, together with the parents and community members are involved in the SDRRM Team.	4.729	Very High	4
information is gathered, stored, and disseminated.	4.729	Very High	4
administrators know how to manage information on any phase of the disaster.	4.771	Very High	1.5
the community stakeholders are engaged and actively participate in the assessing, planning, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating education in emergency programs.	4.521	Very High	9
the learners understand and participate in DRRM activities.	4.667	Very High	6
capacity building is included in the School Improvement Plan.	4.729	Very High	4
risk assessment and training needs analysis are conducted.	4.604	Very High	7
training of the school community is maximized through partnerships with NGOs and CSOs.	4.521	Very High	9
contingency plans are present in case hazards incur.	4.521	Very High	9

Average Weighted Mean	4.656	Very High	
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Table 7. Extent of Implementation of the Three Pillars of the Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education in terms of Risk Reduction and Resilience Education

Pillar III Risk Reduction and Resilience Education	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
classroom teaching of DRRM is implemented in all grade levels and subject areas such as Science, Araling Panlipunan, and Health.	4.792	Very High	1
classroom teaching of DRRM is complemented with co-curricular activities and local and national activities.	4.646	Very High	3
learning materials are made available by the SDRRM Team.	4.458	High	4
DepEd goals on food security, biodiversity conservation, and climate change mitigation and adaptation are integrated such as participation in the national greening program.	4.750	Very High	2
Average Weighted Mean	4.661	Very High	

Table 8. Significant Relationship between the Level of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes of Teachers on the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education and the Extent of Implementation of the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

Competency	Pillar	χ^2 Value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Knowledge	Pillar1	8.988	0.704	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
	Pillar2	6.235	0.397	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
	Pillar3	5.362	0.498	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Skills	Pillar1	7.576	0.817	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
	Pillar2	7.462	0.28	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

	Pillar3	8.46	0.206	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Attitude	Pillar1	25.014	0.001	Reject H_0	Significant
	Pillar2	31.694	0.001	Reject H_0	Significant
	Pillar3	21.626	0.001	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 9. Significant Relationship between the Profile of the School and Level of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes of Teachers on the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

Profile of School	Competency	χ^2 Value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Location	Knowledge	9.351	0.673	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Enrollment		13.134	0.359	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Position		17.788	0.122	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
DRRM Coordinator		16.253	0.575	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
SBM Level		5.688	0.459	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
CFSS Level		7.554	0.819	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Location	Skills	11.18	0.514	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Enrollment		23.658	0.023	Reject H_0	Significant
Position		16.152	0.184	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
DRRM Coordinator		19.268	0.376	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
SBM Level		6.901	0.33	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
CFSS Level		14.02	0.299	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Location	Attitude	2.985	0.56	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Enrollment		2.651	0.618	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Position		3.268	0.514	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
DRRM Coordinator		6.528	0.367	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

SBM Level		1.112	0.574	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
CFSS Level		4.944	0.293	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

Table 10. Significant Relationship between the Profile of the School and the Extent of Implementation of the Three Pillars of the Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

Profile of School	Pillar	χ^2 Value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Location	I	2.354	0.671	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Enrollment		2.065	0.724	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Position		2.601	0.627	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
DRRM Coordinator		5.053	0.537	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
SBM Level		5.861	0.053	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
CFSS Level		9.947	0.041	Reject H_0	Significant
Location	II	0.827	0.661	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Enrollment		0.607	0.738	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Position		0.703	0.704	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
DRRM Coordinator		4.168	0.244	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
SBM Level		2.246	0.134	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
CFSS Level		8.43	0.015	Reject H_0	Significant
Location	III	0.403	0.817	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Enrollment		0.356	0.837	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Position		2.499	0.287	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
DRRM Coordinator		1.747	0.626	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
SBM Level		4.692	0.044	Reject H_0	Significant
CFSS Level		8.798	0.012	Reject H_0	Significant

DISCUSSION

Disasters are sudden catastrophes that ravage everything and take away human lives. It is categorized into 1. natural disasters or disasters that humans cannot control, such as floods, fire, and earthquakes; and 2. man-made disasters due to the implications that human beings themselves cause certain disasters, and some of these acts are warfare, vandalism, and cyber-attacks among others (Brown, 2018). Assessment of the three pillars of the comprehensive disaster risk reduction management in basic education was completed through a survey method. The results from the data gathered will be presented and discussed this in chapter.

While the DRRM act provided a legal basis for its disaster risk reduction directives, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued DO 37, s. 2015 as the basis of the Basic Education Framework with a more comprehensive Disaster Risk Reduction Management. Catanus (2018) stated that in this framework, the offices, and schools of DepEd shall have institutionalized DRRM structures, systems, protocols, and practices. Moreover, the impact of disasters always finds their way in schools through strong typhoons and massive flooding that ruins school properties. Thus, Philippines being prone to disaster warrant a closer look at its disaster-related policies that are currently in place (Mamhot, 2019).

Although numerous different programs have been developed, there are still very few studies on the program awareness and implementation in educational institutions. Thus, to fill in the gap in existing literature, this study included the profile of the school to determine the extent of implementation of the public schools' DRRM program.

Profile of the School

The researcher wanted to test the relationships between the profile of the school. Among the 48 public schools who participated in the survey, only 4 schools lie within the town proper, 26 of the schools are located in the lowland, and the remaining 18 are located upland. The school enrolment profile shows that the majority of the schools who participated in the survey have an enrollment of less than 250 students, having a percentage of 70.83. this was followed by those schools whose enrollment was between 251 to 500 with a frequency of 10 and has a percentage of 20.83. Last was the 4 schools whose enrollment was 751 and above with a percentage of 8.33.

As for the school head's position, 20 out of 48 (41.67%) respondents have a principal item, 14 (29.17) head teacher, and 14 (29.17) are teacher-in-charge. For the school DRRM coordinators, the following are the breakdown of the number of participants: 20 (41.67%) Teacher I, 13 (27.08%) Teacher II, 14 (29.17%) Teacher III, and 1 (2.08%) Head/ Master Teacher.

The majority of the participating schools, 38 out of 48 (79.17%) belong to Level II (Maturing) of the SB Level, and the remaining 10 (20.83%) are on Level III (Advanced). With regards to the CFSS, 8 (16.67%) schools have a score of 30 and below, 10 (20.83%)

schools have a score between 31- 35, and the majority of the schools, 30 (62.50%) have a score between 36 to 40.

Level of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes of Teachers on the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

The decisive role of a teacher has called upon the necessity to employ a range of measurement standards and accreditation to ensure the students who graduate from a certain program meet employer requirements. In the past years, a teacher's competency has attracted much attention among researchers and become the main concern among educational stakeholders. In the study of Omar et al. (2020), the pertinent facts from their research findings indicated salient contributions to understanding teacher competence in the teaching profession.

The researchers pushed the research context within teacher competency, imploring the necessary action toward understanding teacher's competency to improve the teaching and learning environment (Low et al., 2016). In a study, it was indicated that the pivotal role of competency consists of knowledge, skills, and attitudes as characteristics and personalities that one person must possess to showcase his or her competence in fulfilling the designated job. The main purpose of competency is to enable someone to perform more tasks effectively and effectively at their optimum level (Nousiainen et al., 2018).

In Table 1, an Item analysis of the level of knowledge of the teachers on the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education is presented. The MPS score is 77.50. Based on the difficulty index of the 10-item test, item 2 "National and provincial hazard maps have been prepared to increase knowledge of risks and at the same time influence development of policies and programs (a. Hazard Map)" has the greatest number of correct answers.

On the contrary, the least number of correct answers was item 9 "Which is identified as the understanding of the geographic area affected, along with the intensity and frequency of hazard events, planning evacuation routes, creating shelters, and running preparedness drills (a. Preparedness)". Out of the 48 respondents, 8 (17%) got a perfect score of 10 in the knowledge of teachers on the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM.

In Table 3, an Item analysis of the level of skills of the teachers on the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education is presented. The MPS score is 82.50. The highest score was 10, and the lowest was 4. Based on the difficulty index of the 10-item test, item 1 "It is the provision of initial care for an ill or injured person. (a. First Aid)" has the greatest number of correct answers. On the contrary, the least number of correct answers was item 7 "In doing CPR, how many breaths should be given every 5 seconds? (a. 1)". Out of the 48 respondents, 13 (27.08%) got a perfect score of 10 in the skills of teachers on the three pillars of comprehensive DRRM.

For Table 4, the level of attitudes of teachers on the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM, the average weighted mean was computed at 4.59 and has the interpretation of very high. Of the 10 competencies itemized under the attitude, Drills for disaster preparedness conducted every quarter got the highest weighted mean of 4.85 and was interpreted as very high. The lowest mean was 4.06, stating that transport of emergency cases is simple because there is an available transport service, which was interpreted as high. The other eight components have an average ranging from 4.73 to 4.48, all interpreted as to be very high.

Table 4. Level of Attitudes of Teachers on the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

These competencies in the knowledge, skills, and attitude of teachers imply that they were very highly competent in the three pillars of comprehensive disaster risk reduction management. Teachers conducted drills for disaster preparedness quarterly, attended DRRM-related trainings and workshops, always prepared disaster kits as ready and available, always monitored the news and forecasts as they prepared for disasters and calamities, and placed the emergency hotlines and evacuation maps in strategic locations in case of emergency. They also conduct hazard mapping in their respective schools to check and prevent any occurrence of accidents due to hazards.

Table 5 implies a very high extent of implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in basic education in terms of Safe Learning Facilities. They practice the promotion of basic health and hygiene through the provision of adequate hand-washing facilities in every school. Schools also have a feeding program to address hunger needs.

The community can make decisions concerning the location of the learning environment and establish systems and policies to ensure that learners are safe and secure as the Department of Education (DepEd) reiterates the provisions of DO 037, s. 2022, which provides guidelines on the cancellation or suspension of classes and work in schools in the event of natural disasters, power outages/power interruptions, and other calamities. This includes the school heads' authority and discretion to suspend the conduct of in-person classes and shift to alternative delivery modes (ADM) in cases of extreme heat and other calamities that may compromise the health and safety of learners, teachers, and non-teaching personnel.

Table 6 shows the extent of implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in basic education in terms of school disaster management with an average weighted mean of 4.656, interpreted as very high.

This implies that all SDRRM was headed by the school head, teachers, and other school personnel, together with the stakeholders are also involved in the team. Schools also include DRRM in the SIP, AIP, and APP for proper procurement of DRRM supplies and budgeting on capacity building. DRRM information is well-managed and properly disseminated.

In Table 7, the extent of implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education in terms of risk reduction and resilience education is presented. The average weighted mean was 4.661 and was interpreted as very high.

This implies that DRRM is integrated into classroom teaching in all grade levels and subject areas such as Science, Araling Panlipunan, and Health. This integration of classroom teaching of DRRM is complemented by co-curricular activities and local and national activities. There were also available learning materials.

Significant Relationship between the Level of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes of Teachers on the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education and the Extent of Implementation of the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

The knowledge of teachers was not significantly related to Pillar 1 (Safe Learning Facilities), Pillar 2 (School Disaster Management), and Pillar 3 (Risk Reduction and Resilience Education), the same with the skills but the attitudes were significantly related to the three Pillars. These imply that the knowledge and skills of the teachers were not important to accomplish the three pillars. However, teachers' attitudes were important in attaining the three pillars.

In statistics, a large chi-square value means that data does not fit, then the observed and expected values are not close and the model is a poor fit to the data (Shen, et al., 2022). In this case, the attitude of the teachers does have a significant relationship with regards to the implementation of comprehensive DRRM.

Disaster risk reduction management has been integrated into all schools to ensure that students and teachers are prepared in the event of a disaster or hazard. This study by Fale (2022) aimed to determine the extent of climate change adaptation, disaster risk reduction management practices, and resiliency of secondary school teachers by utilizing a descriptive and correlational design.

The findings revealed that secondary school teachers' level of climate change adaptation was very satisfactory. The disaster risk reduction management practices of secondary school teachers were also very satisfactory. Secondary school teachers' resiliency in terms of absorptive and anticipatory capacity was rated very satisfactory, while transformative capacity was rated satisfactory.

Another significant finding is that the secondary teachers engaged in an acceptable practice of eradicating disaster risk through mitigation. Teachers tend to provide adequate knowledge of the various types of disasters that are likely to occur and ways to protect against them by incorporating them into their curriculum.

Significant Relationship between the Profile of the School and Level of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes of Teachers on the Three Pillars of Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

The study of Lavilles and Hordista (2024), determined the level of awareness of the teachers and administrators in natural and human-caused disasters as well as their level of preparation and implementation of the DRRM Program using descriptive-correlational research design, specifically, weighted mean and Pearson Correlation. Results of the study showed a high awareness of teachers and administrators in natural and human-caused disasters. The school personnel also prepared and implemented the DRRM Program. The study also revealed significant relationships between the awareness of multiple disasters and preparation in the DRRM Program as well as the preparation and implementation of the DRRM Program. Given the overall results, the study may serve as a basis for schools to improve the implementation of the DRRM Program through higher disaster awareness and preparation.

In line with this, the Department of Education (DepEd) included the Disaster Readiness and Risk Reduction (DRRR) subject in the K-12 Senior High School curriculum after launching the K-12 program in 2013. However, after reviewing the curricula of two selected schools from the Philippines, it was discovered that the DRRR subject was only offered in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math (STEM) strand as a required subject while it is offered in the General Academic (GAS) strand as either a required subject or an elective. Furthermore, DepEd itself prescribed DRRR as a core subject only for STEM, with the other strands not required to take this subject. Therefore, it is recommended for DepEd to revisit the Senior High School curricula and try to include Disaster Readiness and Risk Reduction as a required subject in all Senior High School strands in order to prepare the next generation in dealing with various hazards in the Philippines (Manalo & Manalo, 2020).

This study by Simon et al. (2021) was conducted to determine the level of resiliency to natural disasters of CAPSU as Basis to Strengthen Disaster Risk Reduction Management Program. The results of the study showed that faculty and staff respondents showed a high level of resiliency, observed 5R's and recorded cellphone hotline numbers. They participated in earthquake/fire drill, tree growing projects, volunteers on community recovery/clean - up drive.

The student who responded in the same study developed the skills in the four DRRM thematic areas but not in high extent, practiced "Drop, Cover, and Hold-on," unplug appliances, and turn - off gas supply, attended preparedness lectures; and volunteer services. Second district Campus/ Satellite colleges showed a high level of resiliency because these are areas prone to floods, soil erosion and earthquakes. It was also found that the lesser the number of faculty and staff and student population the easier it is to implement DRRM activities. Administration may consider conducting training related to First Aid, and correct handling of fire extinguisher.

From the recommendation of the study, knowledge, skills, and attitude of the teachers can be improved through conduct of workshops and trainings in awareness and preparation. In this case's scenario, different school profiles were tested in relationship with the knowledge, skills, and attitude of the teachers using Chi- Square Test. A significant relationship is established, with 95% level of confidence, between the enrollment profile of the school and the level of skills of the teachers on the extent of implementation of the comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education.

This implies that the competencies on the skills of the teachers such as prevention of illness and diseases, provision of first aid has a significant relationship with the number of enrollments.

Significant Relationship between the Profile of the School and the Extent of Implementation of the Three Pillars of the Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

In this part of the study, the school's profile, and the extent of implementation of the three pillars of the comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education was tested for relationship using chi- square test. Results revealed a significant relationship between CFSS Level and Pillar I (Safe Learning Facilities), between CFSS Level and Pillar II (School Disaster Management), and between SBM Level and CFSS Level and Pillar III (Risk Reduction and Resilience Education). Their large chi- square value indicated that the above-mentioned profile has a significant relationship with the extent of implementation of the comprehensive DRRM.

The results revealed that the participants have very satisfactory awareness in the fields of enabling environment, safe learning facilities, disaster risk management, and risk reduction and resilience education and have shown satisfactory compliance in the same fields. Findings of their study indicated that DRRM is not emphasized in the schools. It was concluded that giving focus on school DRRM and conduct of relevant DRRM activities are important to establish resilience in schools.

The test of hypotheses conducted in this study has recognized the significant relationship between variables that are notably important to the teachers, schools, pillars of the DRRM, and most importantly to the learners. Just as Taluban, et al., (2023) in their study determined the disaster awareness and adaptation practices among senior high school students. A descriptive research design was employed through questionnaires.

Based on the data gathering by the researchers' findings show that in terms of disaster awareness, the respondents know the importance of disaster/emergency drills in school. Meanwhile, in terms of disaster adaptation practices of students at home the data reveals that the respondents are always updated in weather condition, temperature, and their surroundings.

On the other hand, as to disaster adaption practices of the respondents at school the data shows that the school disseminates enough information about evacuation areas or safe spot during and after disaster/ emergency situations inside the vicinity of the school.

Common and Best Practices of Elementary and Secondary Schools with regards with the Implementation of the Three Pillars of the Comprehensive DRRM in Basic Education

Amongst the 48 participating schools in the study, the most common practice for safe learning facilities is their accessibility to any physical ability and basic health and hygiene are promoted in the learning environment. This implies that public schools are great followers and advocates in conducting drills and other DRRM activities. Most schools' best practices include active community participation of the external stakeholders in the construction and maintenance of the school every *Brigada Eskwela*.

This study also implied a well-established School DRRM in schools. Common practice is the participation in the quarterly NSED. Notable best practices of some schools were the use of online platforms to disseminate information of DRRM, specifically on their official FB Page, also some schools include procurement of DRRM materials in their MOOE budget through inclusion in the School Improvement Plan and Annual Improvement Plan. Aside from these, schools tied up with the LGU and other NGOs in the conduct of workshops and trainings.

For Risk Reduction and Resilience Education, the most common practice is the classroom teaching of DRRM at all levels. This implies that teachers are highly proficient in classroom integration of the DRRM lessons. Significant practices of some schools are coordinating with other stakeholders and inviting them as speakers and training managers to be able to integrate such into the curriculum.

Conclusions

After analyzing the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: Teachers in Santa Maria Sub- Office are more equipped with knowledge, skilled, and possessed a positive attitude towards DRRM implementation especially those teachers in schools with lower enrolment. Since DRRM is part of the curriculum, Child Friendly School Survey (CFSS) and School-Based Management level also has an effect on its implementation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were formulated after carefully drawing the conclusions: To support teachers who are knowledgeable, skilled, and competent in DRRM, continuous training of teachers, school administrators, facilitators, and staff are highly encouraged to keep them posted of the DRRM practices, methods, and advisories. Development of monitoring and evaluation tools to properly monitor and evaluate the implementation of the DRRM activities in schools.

Establish more schools to keep the enroll low and encourage the schools to attain an advanced level in the SBM. DepEd, together with the National Government should keep

teachers and schools motivated in instigating DRRM activities to learners by providing learning materials.

School enrollment should be kept at medium scale for accurate and constant monitoring of DRRM activities. Schools can partner with the LGUs and other stakeholders to be able to continuously provide a healthier environment for the learners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers obtained informed consent from all participants, ensuring their right to withdraw at any time. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout the study. There were no conflicts of interest, and the research adhered to ethical guidelines, avoiding plagiarism and bias. The results are solely for research purposes.

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